

Histopathological Study of Colorectal Adenocarcinomas

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Abstract:

Background: Colorectal carcinoma is the most common malignancy of the gastrointestinal tract. Adenocarcinomas account for 90% of the colorectal carcinomas.

Objective: This is a study to evaluate histopathologically the colorectal adenocarcinomas based on age, sex distribution and grading.

Materials and methods: The study comprises of 50 paraffin blocks of all patients who were histopathologically diagnosed as having colorectal adenocarcinoma in the Department of Pathology, Rajshahi Medical College.

Results - Out of total 50 cases, most 13 (26%) cases belonged to the age group of 51-60 years. The age group ranged from 20-75 years with a mean age 51.2 ± 13.74 . There were 40 (80%) males and 10 (20%) females with male to female ratio 4:1. Rectum being the most common site of involvement (36%) followed by ascending colon, sigmoid colon and descending colon. In this study, most 20 (40%) were grade 3 tumors, followed by 18 (36%) grade 2 tumors and 12 (24%) grade 1 tumors.

Conclusion- This study has showed grade 3 tumors outnumbered the grade 2 and grade 1 tumors. Histopathologic diagnosis remain paramount importance in accurate diagnosis of colorectal adenocarcinomas with grading and predict prognosis.

Keywords: Adenocarcinoma, Tumor grade

Introduction:

Cancers which arise in the colon or rectum have many features in common and are therefore referred together as colorectal carcinoma. Colorectal cancer is the most common malignancy of the gastrointestinal tract and ranks third in terms of

incidence and second in mortality, Overall. More than 1.9 million new colorectal cancer cases and 9,35,000 death are estimated to occur in 2020, representing about 1 in 10 cancer cases and deaths.¹ According to GLOBOCAN 2020, the prevalence of colon and rectal cancer in Bangladesh are 3.28% and 3.15% respectively in last five years.² Adenocarcinomas account for 90% of the colorectal carcinomas. It is graded as well, moderately and poorly differentiated mainly on the regularity of the glandular architecture as per the WHO classification.³

Mucinous adenocarcinoma is a subtype of colorectal adenocarcinoma with more than 50% of the lesion composed of mucin and is characterized by pools of extracellular mucin that contain malignant epithelium as acinar structures, strips of cells or single cells. The colorectal carcinoma cases with less than 20% mucin are categorized as mild, those cases with 20-50% mucin as moderate and those with more than 50% mucin as marked.³

Lower grade cancers tend to grow slowly and are less likely to spread while higher grade cancers tend to grow more quickly and are more likely to spread

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than low-grade cancers. This helps in planning the treatment. The grade can also help the healthcare team predict future outcomes (Prognosis) and how the cancer might respond to treatment.⁴

According to WHO histological grading system 2010,

Well differentiated (Grade 1): Lesions exhibit glandular structures in >95% of the tumor.

Moderately differentiated (Grade 2): Glandular structures comprise 50-95% of the tumor.

Poorly differentiated (Grade 3): comprise 0- <49% of the gland formation.

Despite advances in surgical techniques and adjuvant chemotherapeutic regimens, colorectal carcinoma remains one of the major leading causes of cancer-related deaths worldwide.⁴

This study was undertaken to evaluate histopathologically the colorectal adenocarcinomas based on age, sex and grading and to compare our experience with findings in this literature.

Materials and Methods:

The present study was carried out in the Department of Pathology, Rajshahi Medical College from March 2021 to February 2023. It comprises 50 paraffin blocks of all patients, who were histopathologically diagnosed as having colorectal adenocarcinomas in this department. All histopathologically confirmed colorectal adenocarcinoma cases were included in this study. Poorly fixed sample were excluded. Hematoxylin and Eosin stain was done according to the protocol followed in the Department of Pathology, Rajshahi Medical College. Slides of all cases were examined and then they were graded as well (grade 1), moderate (grade 2) and poorly (grade 3) differentiated carcinomas.

Results:

The present study includes 50 cases of colorectal adenocarcinomas reported in the Department of Pathology, Rajshahi Medical College. The age group ranged from 20-75 years with a mean age 51.2±13.74. Most 13 (26%) cases belonged to the age group of 51-60 years. 3 (6%) cases were less than 30 years, 10 (20%) cases were within 31-40 years, 12 (24%) cases were within 41-50 years and 12 (24%) were in the age group of more than 60 years.

Table-I shows the age wise distribution of colorectal adenocarcinomas in our study.

Table-I: Distribution of the study subjects by their age (n=50)

Age (years)	Frequency	Percentage
31-40	10	20%
41-50	12	24%
51-60	13	26%
> 60	12	24%
Mean±SD	51.2 ±13 .74 (20-75)	

Range (Min-Max)

There were 40 (80%) males and 10(20%) females with a male to female ratio 4:1. Figure - 1 shows gender distribution.

Figure-1: Pie chart showing gender distribution (n=50)

Out of 50 cases, most were located in the rectum 18 (36%), followed by ascending Colon 16 (32%), sigmoid colon 13 (26%) and descending colon 3(6%). Figure - 2 shows distribution of cases according to the site of the tumor.

Figure-2: Pie chart showing distribution of cases according to the site of the tumor (n=50)

Most 20(40%) were grade-3 tumors, followed by 18 (36%) grade 2 tumors and 12 (24%) grade 1 tumors. Figure-3 shows distribution of study subjects according to tumor grade.

Figure-3: Bar diagram showing distribution of study subjects according to tumor grade (n=50)

Figure-4: Photograph showing cut section of colorectal carcinoma specimen

Figure-5: Photograph showing cut section of colorectal carcinoma specimen

Figure-6: Photomicrograph shows grade 1 colorectal adenocarcinoma (H&E)

Figure-7: Photomicrograph shows grade 2 colorectal adenocarcinoma (H&E)

Figure-8: Photomicrograph shows grade 3 colorectal adenocarcinoma (H&E)

Discussion:

Colorectal cancer is the most common malignancy of the gastrointestinal tract and ranks third in terms of incidence and second in terms of mortality.¹ Adenocarcinomas account for most colorectal carcinomas, about 90%.³ Colorectal adenocarcinoma is a heterogeneous disease that involves multiple tumorigenic pathways. Prediction of prognosis in colorectal cancer is vital for the choice of therapeutic options. Histopathologic diagnosis remains paramount in this aspect.⁶

Since gross and histopathological evaluation is very essential to grade and stage the tumor and guide in further management, we have attempted to evaluate the histopathological grading of colorectal adenocarcinoma. This present study included 50 colorectal adenocarcinoma cases.

The age group ranged from 20-75 years with a mean age 51.2±13.74. Out of 50 total study cases, most 40 (80%) were males and 10 (20%) were females. In India, Borgohain et al.³ Conducted a similar study on colorectal adenocarcinoma. A total of 50 cases of histologically confirmed colorectal carcinoma irrespective of age and sex were studied. The peak

incidence was seen between 40-49 years with maximum cases in between 30-70 years of age and predominantly the cases were males. Another study conducted by Parul et al.⁷ showed that the age interval of patients was from 23 to 78 year, the median age being 53 years. Most (82-22%) of the cases occurred in patients above 40 years of age. The male: female ratio was 1.4:1. There were 52 (57.77%) male patients and 38 (42.22%) female patients. In current study most tumors were in the rectum 18 (36%), followed by ascending colon 16 (32%), sigmoid colon 13 (26%) and descending colon 3 (6%). Another study, was conducted by Lucky et al.⁸ on colorectal adenocarcinoma and it was seen that the commonest site of growth was rectum (59%) followed by ascending colon (16%), transverse colon (12%), sigmoid colon (8%) and descending colon (6%). Parul et al.⁷ found that most (40%) of the carcinomas had a right colonic location followed by rectum with 24.44% of cases. Left colon accounted for 20% of the cases, where as rectosigmoid region accounted for 15.55% cases.

In this current study out of 50 colorectal adenocarcinoma, cases, most 20 (40%) were grade 3 tumors, followed by 18 (36%) grade 2 tumors and 12 (24%) grade 1 tumors. In a study conducted by lucky et al.⁷ it was found that out of the 50 cases there were 41 (82%) low grade tumors and 9 (18%) high grade tumors.

Conclusion:

In our study, high grade tumors outnumbered the low grade tumors. The study shows histopathological evaluation is essential to grade and predict future prognosis.

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